

DELAMINATION FRACTURE FROM SURFACE NOTCH

IN $[(\pm 45^\circ)/90^\circ/0^\circ]_S$ GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Damage tolerance has been of great concern in the serviceability of advanced fiber reinforced composite structures. Delamination initiated from a service-induced surface notch has long been regarded as one of the most frequently encountered types of damage. Understanding the failure behavior of this kind is of fundamental importance for the assurance of the reliability and performance of the material. This paper presents an analytical study on the delamination fracture emanating from a surface notch in commonly used $[(\pm 45^\circ)/90^\circ/0^\circ]_S$ graphite/epoxy fiber reinforced composites.

The composite is modeled as an assembly of anisotropic elastic plies bonded together by thin matrix interlayers. The matrix dominated delamination crack is introduced in the resin-rich region, and the surface notch takes the form of broken plies of the composites. Results on delamination fracture in 8-ply $[(\pm 45^\circ)/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ graphite/epoxy composites subjected to a uniaxial nominal stress are obtained by using a hybrid-stress finite element method with a crack-tip superelement formulated through Muskhelishvili's complex stress functions. Crack-tip stress field and its through-thickness distributions are presented for the cases of various geometric and laminate parameters. Stress transfer mechanisms in the laminate are elucidated; interlaminar stresses are found to be very high and localized within the resin-rich interlayer ahead of the crack tip, and the in-plane stress concentration with a rapidly increasing gradient in transverse direction are observed in the adjacent ply. The effects of stacking sequence and the depth of the surface notch on failure modes and mechanisms are found to be significant. Of particular interest are the combined mode stress intensity factors, K_I and K_{II} ; their magnitudes are precisely determined in the paper. The results reveal many important features of composite delamination failure, and provide basic insight into the nature of the damage resistance of the material. Furthermore, implications of current results on delamination fracture under adverse environment and fatigue loading are also discussed.

I. Introduction

Damage tolerance has been of great concern in the reliability of advanced fiber-reinforced composites. Delamination fracture is considered one of the most commonly encountered types of damage in the material during service. The presence and growth of the delamination may have a significant effect on the performance of the composites. It may cause a significant reduction of structural stiffness, the exposure of the interior to adverse environmental attack and progressive structural disintegration, which may lead to final failure. Thus, understanding the delamination behavior is of fundamental importance in the design and testing of the material. This paper presents an analytical study on delamination fracture initiated from a service-induced surface notch in $[(\pm 45^\circ)/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ graphite/epoxy composites.

The particular class of ply configuration is chosen in this study because this is one of the most interesting and widely used laminate layup of composites in many advanced engineering structures such as pressure vessels and aircraft constructions. The $[(\pm 45^\circ)/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ fiber composite, also called $\pi/4$ laminate or quasi-isotropic laminate, consists of equal percentages of 0° , 45° , -45° and 90° plies and resin-rich interlaminar regions between the plies. The plies possess a symmetry with respect to the laminate mid-plane, and the interlaminar region usually has a dimension of one twentieth to one tenth of the individual ply thickness. Delamination, sometimes known as interlaminar fracture, is generally considered a resin or matrix dominated failure behavior, and usually occurs in the interlayer where strength is low and local strain is high, as shown in Fig. 1. Potential causes to initiate the delamination

Fig. 1 Micrograph of Graphite/Epoxy Composite Showing Delamination Crack in Resin-Rich Interlayer

failure include geometric discontinuities, processing and machining defects, and service and manufacturing flaws. Studies have been conducted to investigate the delamination caused by geometric discontinuities [1,2,3], but relatively little attention has been given to the interlaminar fracture associated with the in-service and manufacturing defects, which involve surface damage taking the form of broken plies.

The importance of the delamination problem has long been recognized, but research progress in understanding and predicting the failure has been slow since this kind of real-life defect is characteristically difficult to study due to inherent complexities of the crack geometry, materials anisotropy and discontinuity, and crack-tip singularity. Because of the matrix dominated fracture mechanism and its very localized nature, it would be unwise to make any simplification which fails to consider the presence and response of the important resin-rich region in the present problem. Furthermore, laminate and geometric parameters such as fiber orientation, ply stacking sequence, delamination depth, and traction boundary conditions seem to make the problem intractable.

II. Mechanical Model and Assumptions

The composite laminate is modeled as an assembly of anisotropic plies bonded by thin isotropic interlayers of polymeric resin, and is assumed to be perfectly bonded everywhere except where delamination is initiated from the tip of the surface notch shown in Fig. 2. Each individual ply and each interlayer have thicknesses of t_0 and t_1 , respectively. For simplicity but

Fig. 2 Delamination Crack Geometry and Coordinate System

without loss of generality, the interlaminar crack is assumed to be completely embedded in the resin-rich region. Studies on the extreme cases such as $t_1 = 0$ and an interlaminar crack located at the ply/interlayer interface, giving a more complicated oscillating crack-tip singularity, are reported elsewhere [4]. In this paper, the delamination crack geometry and laminate layup are conveniently expressed by $(\theta_1/\theta_2//\theta_3/\theta_4/\theta_5/\dots)_S$, where θ_i is the angle between fiber orientation and loading direction in the i th ply. The double slash indicates the location of the delamination and the underline represents the penetration depth of the surface notch.

III. Method of Analysis

The current approach based on an advanced singular finite-element method of hybrid-stress model has a capability to overcome the difficulties, and can provide a numerically exact solution for the problem. The method, pioneered by Pian [5] and later refined by Tong, et al. [6], gives a rapid rate of convergence of solutions, and enables an accurate description of the crack-tip response by introducing a crack-tip superelement based on the complex variable formulation of Muskhelishvili stress functions, including singular and non-singular higher order terms. It has the capacity of solving crack problems with complex material and structural parameters, and has the advantages of exact modeling of the traction boundary conditions of crack surfaces. Additional features of the method include the flexibility of formulation, the selection of element features, and the expedient achievement of interelement compatibility.

The general procedure of formulation for the plane delamination crack problem in the composites is given in this section. Details of the formulation for the crack-tip superelement and surrounding non-singular elements have been described elsewhere [6,7]; thus, only a brief outline is given here.

The formulation of the analysis is based on the variational principle of the modified complementary energy. The functional π_m to be minimized has the form

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_m = & \int_{\partial A} (\tilde{u}_i - u_i) T_i ds - \int_{s_\sigma} \tilde{u}_i \bar{T}_i ds \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \iint_A [\sigma_{ij}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) - S_{ijkl} \sigma_{ij} \sigma_{kl}] dA \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{T}_i is the prescribed traction over boundary s_σ ; \tilde{u}_i is the prescribed displacement over s_u ; σ_{ij} , u_i and S_{ijkl} are the stress tensor, displacement vector and elastic compliance tensor, respectively, and \tilde{u}_i and T_i are defined over ∂A .

Following Muskhelishvili's formulation, the stress and displacement fields may be expressed in terms of two stress functions, $\phi(z)$ and $\psi(z)$, of a complex variable, $z = x + iy$, as

$$\sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{xx} = 2[\phi'(z) + \overline{\phi'(z)}] \quad (2a)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} - \sigma_{xx} + 2i \sigma_{xy} = 2[z \phi''(z) + \psi'(z)] \quad (2b)$$

and
$$2G(u + iv) = \eta \phi(z) - z \overline{\phi'(z)} - \overline{\psi(z)} \quad (2c)$$

where G is the shear modulus, and η is a plane stress or strain parameter.

A mapping function $w(\xi)$ is introduced to transfer the singular crack domain to a ξ -plane,

$$z = w(\xi) = \xi^2 \quad (3)$$

with

$$-\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \arg \xi \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$$

The functions, $\phi(\xi)$ and $\psi(\xi)$ in ξ -plane, are analytical and interrelated through the traction boundary condition along crack surfaces by

$$i \int_S (T_x + i T_y) ds = \phi(z) + z \overline{\phi'(z)} + \psi(z) = 0 \quad (4)$$

Thus,
$$\psi(\xi) = - \overline{\phi(-\xi)} - \overline{w(-\xi)} \frac{\phi'(\xi)}{w'(\xi)} \quad (5)$$

In the crack-tip superelement formulation, $\phi(\xi)$ is assumed to have the form

$$\phi(\xi) = \sum^N b_j \xi^j \quad (6)$$

and function $\psi(\xi)$ may be obtained as

$$\psi(\xi) = - \sum^N [\bar{b}_j (-1)^j + \frac{1}{2} b_j] \xi^j \quad (7)$$

where
$$b_j = \beta_j + i \beta_{N+j} \quad (\text{non-symmetric case}) \quad (8)$$

or
$$b_j = \beta_j \quad (\text{symmetric case}) \quad (9)$$

and β_s are real constants to be determined.

Using Eqs. 6 and 7, the stress and displacement fields in Eqs. 2a,b,c may be expressed in terms of the stress coefficients β_s . The boundary traction \underline{T} can be calculated by

$$T_i = \sigma_{ij} v_j \quad (10)$$

Interpolating boundary displacements \tilde{u} in terms of nodal displacements q and inserting σ and \underline{T} into the variational energy principle, the crack-tip superelement stiffness matrix $\tilde{k}^{(s)}$ may be obtained.

Surrounding non-singular elements are formulated by a conventional hybrid-stress finite element method through the minimum complementary energy principle [8],

$$\pi_r = \iint_A \frac{1}{2} S_{ijkl} \sigma_{ij} \sigma_{kl} dA - \int_S \bar{u}_i T_i ds \quad (11)$$

The anisotropic elastic properties of each graphite/epoxy ply are considered in the analysis by introducing appropriate compliance matrices $\underline{S}^{(r)}$ in the element stiffness formulation,

$$\underline{S}^{(r)} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{16} \\ S_{21} & S_{22} & S_{26} \\ S_{61} & S_{62} & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Since boundary displacement functions are independently assumed for the super-element and non-singular elements, interelement compatibility can be ensured by a suitable choice of interpolation functions.

The assembled governing equations for the whole system may be written as

$$\underline{K}q = Q \quad (13)$$

where \underline{K} is the global stiffness matrix, and Q , the consistent loading vector.

After solving q from Eq. 13 by an appropriate solution scheme, the stress and strain fields can be determined. Stress intensity factors K_I and K_{II} may be found from the relation

$$K_I = \sqrt{2\pi} \beta_1 \quad (14a)$$

and

$$K_{II} = \sqrt{2\pi} \beta_{N+1} \quad (14b)$$

The associated elastic energy release rates, G_I and G_{II} , therefore, can be obtained.

The accuracy and convergence assessments of solutions are complicated by several unusual features of the problem and of the method of analysis due to the singular nature of the delamination crack tip. A study of the accuracy and convergence of the analysis, and solution stability has been made by testing cases for which independent solutions are available. Details of the study are reported elsewhere [7]. Excellent agreements with existing closed-form solutions are observed. The results also indicate that accuracy within approximately one percent of the converged solutions of K_I and K_{II} can be obtained for the optimum mesh arrangements used in the current study.

IV. Results and Discussion

Results of the delamination fracture of the 8-ply $[(\pm 45^\circ)/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ graphite/epoxy composites subjected to a uniform nominal stress σ_∞ are presented in this section. The individual graphite/epoxy lamina has a thickness of 0.005 inch, and the interlaminar layer is taken as one-tenth of the ply as observed by an optical microscope. The delamination crack length is assumed to be three times the ply thickness. Elastic constants, typical of a medium-strength graphite/epoxy ply, are given as

$$E_{LL} = 20.0 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}$$

$$E_{TT} = E_{ZZ} = 2.1 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}$$

$$G_{LZ} = 0.85 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}$$

and

$$\nu_{LZ} = 0.21$$

The interlaminar epoxy resin has the properties:

$$E_m = 0.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}$$

$$G_m = 0.185 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}$$

and

$$\nu_m = 0.35$$

A. Stresses Around Delamination Crack

The response of the composite to the presence of the delamination crack is best illustrated by isostress contours around the crack through the laminate thickness. Figure 3 gives an isostress contour plot of the in-plane longitudinal stress distribution $\sigma_{xx}/\sigma_\infty$ for a section of the laminate around the delamination crack. The computer plotted isostress lines in the figure provide only an approximate description of the obtained analytical solution, but can give an overall view of the delamination nature. Several

Fig. 3 In-Plane Longitudinal Stress Contours, $\sigma_{xx}/\sigma_\infty$, Near Delamination Crack Tip in $(0^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ Graphite/Epoxy

salient features of the problem are evident from the results: (a) the intensified stress field of the delamination crack is very localized ahead of the crack tip within the matrix-rich interlayer, (b) a large stress concentration with rapidly increasing gradient occurs in the adjacent ply just above the delamination crack tip, and (c) the far field stress decreases drastically through the thickness, and some local compression along the crack flank is observed.

Figures 4 and 5 show isostress contours of the interlaminar shear and normal stresses in the laminate. Both components have extremely high gradients within the interlaminar region, and extend continuously through the interlayer into adjacent plies. These high stresses indicate a strong tendency to drive the delamination crack growing along the interlaminar region. A more accurate description of the stresses in the near field and their implications on the delamination fracture are discussed in the next sections.

Fig. 5 Interlaminar Shear Stress Contours, $\sigma_{xz}/\sigma_\infty$, Near Delamination Crack Tip in $(0^\circ/45^\circ// -45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ Graphite/Epoxy

Fig. 4 Transverse Normal Stress Contours, $\sigma_{zz}/\sigma_\infty$, Near Delamination Crack Tip in $(0^\circ/45^\circ// -45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ Graphite/Epoxy

B. Delamination Crack-Tip Stress Singularity

The near field stresses ahead of the interlaminar crack in the resin-rich interlayer, shown in Figs. 3-5, can be expressed more precisely by Fig. 6 in which crack-tip stresses are shown along a distance ahead of the delamination. Note that the coordinates are given in a logarithmic scale. All points follow a slope of minus one-half indicating a classical fracture mechanics behavior, i.e. a $1/\sqrt{r}$ singularity. The in-plane and transverse stress components are found to have the same order of magnitude, even when a uniaxial nominal stress is applied. The singular domain is rather small and embedded within the resin interlayer. It will be readily diminished whenever a local yielding or flow of the matrix develops. Thus, the high stress concentration at the interface of the adjacent ply/interlayer may play a very important role in the complex fracture mechanisms of the composites.

Fig. 6 Stresses Ahead of the Delamination Crack Tip in a $(0^{\circ}/45^{\circ} // -45^{\circ}/90^{\circ})_s$ Graphite/Epoxy Composite

C. Stress Concentration in Adjacent Plies

The response of the adjacent plies to the delamination crack in the composites suggests several distinct features of the failure mechanisms unique to the problem. Figure 7 depicts distribution of the in-plane stress $\sigma_{xx}/\sigma_{\infty}$ across the thickness at a small distance ahead of the crack tip. A high level of the in-plane stress in the interlaminar region is observed. A large stress concentration at the ply-interlayer interface with a rapidly increasing gradient in the adjacent ply are also noticed. The highly non-uniform distribution of the stresses in the transverse direction indicates that the classical laminate plate theory may not be applicable to a composite containing a delamination crack, and that it may lead to an intralaminar fracture in the adjacent ply. Furthermore, the introduction of the delamination from the service defect may become very detrimental to the serviceability and reliability of the material when used in an adverse environment such as moisture, corrosive chemicals, or fatigue, because not only does the inter-

Fig. 7 In-plane Longitudinal Stress Gradient, $\sigma_{xx}/\sigma_{\infty}$, Through Laminate Thickness at $x/t_1 = 0.18$

laminar crack expose the interior of the composites to the environmental attack, but also the high stress concentration in the region near the crack surfaces may enhance the rate-dependent degradation.

The peeling failure of the composites is directly related to the opening and sliding modes of the delaminated plies. Current results indicate that both the transverse shear and normal stress components developed at the crack tip may significantly promote the interlaminar fracture. Figure 8 gives a quantitative description for the thickness distribution of the interlaminar normal stress $\sigma_{zz}/\sigma_{\infty}$ ahead of the crack tip. The transverse normal component is noted for having an extremely high level within the thin interlayer. The magnitudes of the opening and sliding modes of the delamination are characterized by crack-tip stress intensity factors. For the composite with the given interlaminar crack and laminate geometry, the delamination stress intensity factors are obtained as

$$\frac{K_I}{(\sqrt{2\pi} \sigma_{\infty})} = 10.96 \times 10^{-2}$$

and

$$\frac{K_{II}}{(\sqrt{2\pi} \sigma_{\infty})} = 12.74 \times 10^{-2}$$

Fig. 8 Interlaminar Normal Stress Distribution, $\sigma_{zz}/\sigma_{\infty}$, Through Laminate Thickness Direction at $x/t_1 = 0.18$

D. Effect of Delamination Depth

Since the delamination crack is initiated from the service-induced surface notch tip, the depth of the interlaminar crack may indicate the degree of damage in the material during service. For the graphite/epoxy composite with the $(0^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ stacking sequence, four different crack depths have been investigated. Figure 9 shows the effect of the crack depth on the delamination crack-tip response. The vertical axis in the figure gives the normalized stress intensity factors, $(K_{I}/\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{\infty})$ and $(K_{II}/\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{\infty})$, and the horizontal coordinate represents the normalized depth of the delamination with respect to $(t_1 + t_0)$, counted from the outer surface of the composite. The results indicate that both the peeling and the sliding modes tend to increase simultaneously by a similar amount as the interlaminar crack moves deeper into the laminate, while only the shearing mode seems to be dominant when the crack is located in the first interlayer. Figure 10 gives normalized stress concentration factors q_{xx} and q_{zz} at the interlayer/ply right above the delamination crack tip. The concentration of stresses in the adjacent ply becomes increasingly significant, as the delamination depth increases.

E. Stacking Sequence Effect

Ply stacking sequence is another laminate parameter which influences the fracture behavior of the composites. Its effect on strength degradation of smooth tensile coupons has been noticed to be very significant in many cases [9,10], but are not known yet for delaminated composites. In this study, a $(0^\circ/45^\circ// -45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ graphite/epoxy with the 90° ply located at different positions is used for illustration. The values of stress intensity factors, K_I , K_{II} , and stress concentrations, q_{ij} , are determined for each case as shown in Tables 1 and 2. The results indicate that delamination crack-tip response is a combined opening and sliding mode fracture of the same order of magnitude, and that stress concentrations in the adjacent plies are not much different for all the cases studied. It should be noted at this point that the failure modes could be very different due to the different fracture resistance of the neighboring plies with various stacking sequences. The high stress concentration and the local stress intensities of the delamination

Fig. 9 Effect of Delamination Crack Depth on Stress Intensity Factors in $[(\pm 45^\circ)/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Composite

Fig. 10 Delamination Crack Depth Effect on Stress Concentration Factors in Adjacent -45° ply, $[(\pm 45^\circ)/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Composite

Table 1. Effect of Ply Stacking Sequence on Delamination Crack-Tip Stress Intensity Factors

Ply Configuration*	$K_I / (\sqrt{2\pi} \sigma_\infty)$	$K_{II} / (\sqrt{2\pi} \sigma_\infty)$
$(0^\circ/45^\circ// -45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$	10.96×10^{-2}	12.74×10^{-2}
$(0^\circ/45^\circ// 90^\circ/-45^\circ)_S$	10.93×10^{-2}	12.85×10^{-2}
$(0^\circ/90^\circ// 45^\circ/-45^\circ)_S$	10.67×10^{-2}	12.22×10^{-2}

*Graphite/epoxy composite

Table 2. Effect of Stacking Sequence on Stress Concentration Factors in Adjacent Ply

Ply Configuration	q_{xx}^*	q_{zz}^*	q_{xz}^*
$(0^\circ/45^\circ// -45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$	7.14	3.12	2.31
$(0^\circ/45^\circ// 90^\circ/-45^\circ)_S$	6.56	3.05	2.32
$(0^\circ/90^\circ// 45^\circ/-45^\circ)_S$	6.85	2.95	2.21

* $q_{xx} = (\sigma_{xx})_{\max} / \sigma_\infty$, $q_{zz} = (\sigma_{zz})_{\max} / \sigma_\infty$ and $q_{xz} = (\sigma_{xz})_{\max} / \sigma_\infty$

crack tip usually lead to two competing failure mechanisms: the interlaminar fracture by which the crack may grow along its own plane, and the intralaminar failure by which the crack changes its course by breaking the adjacent ply. These distinct mechanisms may be studied by independent fracture criteria associated with different failure modes.

The delamination crack growth in unidirectional and cross-ply fiber composites has been successfully predicted by a combined mode fracture criterion, based on calculated stress intensity factors or energy release rates [10]. This criterion is also employed in this study to investigate the interlaminar fracture of the quasi-isotropic laminates. It has the form as

$$G_I + G_{II} = G_c \quad (13a)$$

or,

$$\left[\frac{K_I}{K_{Ic}} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{K_{II}}{K_{IIc}} \right]^2 = 1 \quad (13b)$$

where G_c and K_c are critical energy release rate and stress intensity factor, respectively, obtained from interlaminar fracture tests. Delamination will start to grow whenever one of the criteria (13a) or (13b) is satisfied.

The intralaminar failure of the adjacent ply resulting from the high stress concentration is considered to be controlled by a strength criterion. Taking the interlaminar stresses into account, the intraply fiber fracture mode is related to

$$\frac{\sigma_{xx} \cos^2 \theta}{\sigma_{LL}(s)} = 1 \quad (14)$$

and the intraply trans-fiber fracture mode of the lamina is determined by

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{xx} \sin^2 \theta}{\sigma_{TT}(s)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{xx} \sin \theta \cos \theta}{\sigma_{LT}(s)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{xz} \cos \theta}{\sigma_{TZ}(s)} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (17)$$

where $\sigma_{LL}(s)$, $\sigma_{TT}(s)$, $\sigma_{LT}(s)$ and $\sigma_{TZ}(s)$ are ultimate stresses of a ply under uniaxial loading along fiber direction, transverse to fibers, pure shear, and transverse shear, respectively.

Failure criteria shown above are used in conjunction with the analysis for the cases of different ply stacking sequences by an iterative solution scheme under incremental loading. The predicted failure and experimental results are in very good agreement. Details of the failure modes of four distinct configurations, $(45^\circ/-45^\circ//90^\circ/0^\circ)_s$, $(45^\circ/-45^\circ//0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$, $(45^\circ/0^\circ// -45^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ and $(0^\circ/45^\circ// -45^\circ/90^\circ)_s$, are given in a related paper⁸ [12].

V. Summary and Conclusions

A study has been conducted on the problem of delamination fracture initiated from a service-induced notch in $[(+45^\circ)/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ graphite/epoxy composites. The singular hybrid-stress finite element method, based on Muskhelishvili's complex stress function formulation through a modified minimum complementary energy principle, has been successfully used to investigate the fundamental characteristics of the delamination. Numerical solutions obtained from the analysis elucidate basic failure modes and mechanics of the delaminated crack in the composites with various geometric and laminate parameters. The results indicate that the delamination crack tip singular domain is localized in the resin-rich interlayer and essentially experiences a combined opening and shearing mode fracture, even though a uniaxial nominal stress field is applied. Significant stress concentrations with rapidly increasing gradients in the adjacent ply and within the delaminated interlayer are observed. The complicated interlaminar stress transfer mechanisms in the thickness direction reveal that the classical laminate plate theory may not be applicable to this class of problem. The intensified crack-tip stress field and the stress concentration in the adjacent ply introduce two competing fracture mechanisms: the interlaminar fracture and the intralaminar fracture. Failure criteria associated with the distinct mechanisms are proposed, and predicted fracture modes agree very well with experimental results. Effects of the delamination crack depth and ply stacking sequence are also studied, and found to be very significant. The results reveal many important features of composite delamination fracture, and provide basic insight into the nature of the damage resistance of the material. Furthermore, the implication of current results on delamination failure under adverse environment and fatigue loading is also presented.

VI. References

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